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An Emerging Type of 'Privatisation' at Public Schools and the Role of Political and Social Networks in Accessing Educational 'Elites'

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The recent law adopted in Greece under the new leftist government in 2015 retains 5 out of the 35 Model Schools for the following reason: the principle of 'excellence' underpinning the schools of this type is denounced as being in conflict with the principle of equal opportunities as it promotes the 'elite' education. The new government states that best practices coming from Model Schools operation could provide stable educational background for the rest of schools at public sector.

'Excellence' is highlighted as a major subject in political discourse among governments. The previous government in 2011, in the middle of the economic crisis, during the implementation of the first Memorandum, used the institution of Model Schools to develop a rhetoric concerning the issue of 'excellence' which serves specific ideological purposes, in order to meet the requirements of specific lobbies. In the name of 'excellence', those pressure groups seem to support the project of establishing an educational 'elite' in order to serve the purposes of a competitive society and financial and social development.

Nowadays, the preservation of the institution of Model Schools even by a leftist government which uses denunciatory rhetoric against 'excellence' is the result of lobbying of the upper middle class. The members of this class are classified as 'Pretenders' who lack the financial resources of 'Elites' but try to promote the educational career of their children in every possible way using their economic or social resources available (van Zanten, 2015). The lack of funds for Education and the depreciation of public schools leads the 'Pretenders' to use Model Schools in a sui generis type of 'privatisation' (Ball, 2009) as a way to provide their children with education of high quality.

Therefore, we wonder if Model Schools are capable to offer the opportunity for mobility and access to the networks of national and global educational 'elites' (Tsakiris et al, 2015) by building skills known as 'soft skills' (Maxwell, 2015) which are associated with leadership, communication and developing effective social relations and which are offered by 'elite' institutions in the globalised educational environment. These skills – described as 'talent' in the global labour market – are the privilege of the graduates of specific elite institutions and lead to power positions (Braun et al, 2015). We pose this question because in Greece there is a quasi-monopoly in the market of shaping the educational 'elite', as such skills are cultivated only in expensive private schools and schools with IB (International Baccalaureate) curricula; that is schools attended by students coming from the upper class.

We assume in this study that there are political and social networks, i.e. social structures composed of individuals or institutions which function at institutional, national and international level (Ball and Exley, 2010) exercising influence and shaping our national educational policy regarding the aforementioned issues. We also attempt to highlight the views of various institutional agents and to identify the influence of national and international networks on the direction of Greek educational policy, concerning the role of 'excellence' in the public schools, the possibility of access to national and global education 'elites' and the emerging peculiar type of 'privatisation' at public schools.

From the above, three main research questions arise:

- a) Whether and in what extent the pressure groups that influence the Greek educational policy are related to specific political and social networks at institutional, national and international level?
- b) Whether and in what way these lobbies aim at the pursuit of mobility and access to national and global educational 'elite'?
- c) Whether and in what extent discourse and action of the above mentioned lobbies refer to a sui generis type of 'privatisation'?

Methodology, Methods, Research Instruments or Sources Used

This study is based on archival material collected from the political and public debate in Greece regarding the establishment of the institution of Model Schools. This material was collected from Parliament transcripts, public media (daily printed and electronic press) and conferences, organised by political, social and educational networks and reflects the intentions of the actors involved in various networks dealing with the institution of Model Schools at national and international level.

We attempt to highlight the influence of various actors – through political, social and educational networks – on national education policy regarding 'excellence', which promotes the appropriation of public education aiming at providing mobility and access to national and global educational "elites".

Thus, we carry out a qualitative analysis of a collected archival material comprising approximately 3,000 pages.

The analysis grid of this material is based on two analysis models:

- a) a policy network analysis (Marsh and Smith, 2000) of the policy-making networks which operate and influence the educational policy of the country. It is an interactive model analysis which sets the policy networks as a concept at the meso-level which can be combined with macro- and micro-level analysis, in order to illustrate the dialectical role that policy networks play in understanding how policy is developed and applied (Hay, 2002).
- b) a strategic analysis (Crozier and Friedberg, 1977) where the strategies of interest groups regarding the exercise

